

When Data Defies Demagogy

What We Have Learned from Tall el-Hammam and Its Neighbors

by

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Abstract: Pioneers of any great enterprise often take on legendary status as the authoritative experts of their field. Such a status is certainly warranted at the beginning stages of said enterprise when their initial research, analyses, and conclusions constitute the only body of available information. Over time, the positions proffered by these pioneers become the accepted and traditional points of view that are unquestioningly repeated by succeeding generations. Tradition eventually morphs into demagogy, and anyone who questions the status quo is labeled a heretic and accused of sullyng the reputation of the “greats.” When new information comes to light, however, what should we do with data that defies demagogy? A case in point is the traditionally accepted view of the occupation history of the Middle Ghor versus what we have learned from Tall el-Hammam and its neighbors. Author P. Silvia (TeHEP Field Archaeologist and Director of Scientific Analysis) presents a summary of his research and the implications driven by the data he has compiled.

Fr Alexis Mallon (1875-1934), William F. Albright (1891-1971), Nelson Gleuck (1900-1971), and Kathleen Kenyon (1906-1978) are all well-known for their Cisjordan excavation work. Albright is the acknowledged founder of “biblical archaeology.” Mallon is also known for his work at Teleilat Ghassul. Gleuck is also known for his discovery of an advanced Nabataean civilization on Jordan. Kenyon is quite well-known for her extensive work at Jericho.

Albright, Mallon, and Gleuck are also known for their Transjordan surveys, published in 1925, 1932, and 1951, respectively. There is a problem, however, with their surveys:

- None of their Transjordan surveys included any excavation; instead, they all relied entirely on *surface* surveys.
- Because Iron Age (IA) pottery dominated the surface landscape, Albright concluded that IA people were the initial settlers on the Transjordan side (except at Ghassul, of course).
- Mallon revisited the same sites as Albright and more, but he came to the same conclusion about IA peoples being the original settlers.
- Gleuck relied heavily on the work of his predecessors and added more sites, but he, too, echoed Albright’s original conclusion about the initial settlers.

In 1951, Albright published his book *The Archaeology of Palestine* and included a map of Palestine in which he showed just two settlements immediately north of the Dead Sea—Jericho and Ghassul. This map, published by the then-acknowledged authority on Levantine archaeology, has had a profound effect on subsequent cartographers of Levantine maps for the Bronze Age.

The most widely distributed maps of the region appear as supplements in virtually all versions of the Bible. In support of Genesis 10, which names the border cities of Canaan, most Early Bronze Age (EBA) maps show only Jericho. Some may also show Teleilat Ghassul, even though it was abandoned at the end of the Chalcolithic Period. A few may also show Iktanu, thanks to the work of Kay Prag, who correctly identified it as belonging to this period. Intermediate Bronze Age (IBA) maps are rarely included because there is little geographical information given in Genesis 11. If IBA maps are included at all, they usually show only Jericho north of the Dead Sea. Maps of the Middle Bronze Age (MBA), which is the time of the Abraham (Genesis 12-19), also show only Jericho.

More information about the flat, circular plain immediately north of the Dead Sea has come to light in recent decades, however. In 1976, Yassine catalogued over 120 sites in the eastern half (the Transjordan side) of the Jordan Valley, far more than any previous survey. He noted shallow Pre-pottery Neolithic (PPN) sites located near primary and secondary wadis and a strong Pottery Neolithic (PN) and Chalcolithic Period (CP) presence on the valley. EBA sites were located mainly on the higher hills and represented fortified villages or small cities. IBA sites were located mainly near major wadis and included sprawling, unfortified agricultural sites. Extensive MBA occupation of the valley consisted of large fortified cities surrounded by small or medium-sized villages. LBA presence is essentially missing from the valley floor, except near the Wadi Zerqa in the far north. Many of the sites were reoccupied in the IA, especially IA1b, IA1c, and IA2, but most were abandoned by the end of IA2.

Despite all of this new data, no changes were made to any published maps of this region to acknowledge Yassine's findings. The conclusions of Albright, Mallon, and Gleuck continued to dominate the cartography of this region.

No matter how extensive a surface survey may be, however, surface surveys provide only a limited understanding of occupation history. A more comprehensive understanding is acquired only through excavation. Prior to WWII, only two sites had been excavated: Teleilat Ghassul, excavated by Alexis Mallon and published in 1934; and Jericho, excavated extensively by Kathleen Kenyon, also published in 1934. Additional excavation was conducted at Ghassul by R. Köeppel (1936-38) and R. North (1959). J.B. Hennessey also excavated there briefly in 1967 and later in 1975-77, but his work remains largely unpublished. S. Bourke was last to examine Ghassul and synthesize the accumulated data. The site is, and remains, associated with the Neolithic and Chalcolithic Periods, so it is effectively irrelevant to Bronze Age cartography.

Other than the limited additional excavation at Ghassul, no further excavations in the Jordan Valley occurred until more than a decade following the publication of Yassine's survey. Tall Iktanu was a salvage excavation conducted by Kay Prag, 1988-91, before Jordan began work to widen the road between Amman and the Dead Sea that cuts through the site. From her excavations, Prag concluded that Iktanu was initially occupied during the CP and was continuously occupied into the MBA, although there was a significant decline in occupation at the end of the EBA. She further noted the existence of a relatively brief occupation on the upper tall during IA2. Prag also did a brief, 2-week excavation at the west end of Tall el-Hammam in 1990 and discovered the remnants of an EBA occupation.

Tall Nimrin was also a salvage excavation conducted by James Flannigan, 1990-94, before Jordan began widening the road up the valley to Salt. Flannigan noted continuous occupation of Nimrin from the CP (possibly earlier) through the MBA. His third year of excavation confirmed

a “gap” in the pottery repertoire that lasted through the entirety of the Late Bronze Age (LBA), with a resumption of occupation during IA1b/c that lasted through IA2.

Excavation of Tall el-Hammam was initiated by Steven Collins in 2005 and continues with Season Fifteen in 2020. The revealed settlement history of Tall el-Hammam is virtually identical to Tall Nimrin, except that reoccupation following the LBA gap occurred a little later, during IA2a. Tall Kafrayn was excavated by Thanasis Papadopoulos, 2007-11, and also revealed a similar occupation history. (Note: Although Papadopoulos claimed occupation during the LBA at Tall Kafrayn, a subsequent review of his pottery by Levantine pottery experts from Jordan’s Department of Antiquities noted that his LBA pottery is actually MBA. Thus, the LBA gap in the pottery repertoire at Kafrayn is consistent with Tall el-Hammam and Tall Nimrin.)

The excavations at Iktanu, Nimrin, Hammam, and Kafrayn have all shed new light on the occupation history of the Transjordan side of the valley that can no longer be ignored:

1. Initial settlement of the region was Neolithic-Chalcolithic, not Iron Age.
2. Tall el-Hammam was a significant, fortified urban center during the EBA that remained as such through both the IBA (when urban centers elsewhere throughout the Levant were abandoned) and the MBA (when unfortified urbanization of the Levant resumed).
3. A sudden and complete destruction occurred across the entire Jordan Valley immediately north of the Dead Sea near the end of MB2.
4. A brief, 2-3 decade resettlement of Jericho occurred during the LBA.
5. Resettlement north of Tall el-Hammam at Tall Nimrin occurred in late IA1.
6. Resettlement of Tall el-Hammam and to the south occurred in IA2.
7. Most urban settlements in the area were destroyed and abandoned during the Assyrian conquest of Israel, and the remaining few were destroyed and abandoned during the Babylonian conquest of Judah.

What, then, are we to do with the information gathered from these sites?

1. The sum of the data derived through the exhaustive survey conducted by Yassine and excavations conducted by Prag, Flannigan, Papadopoulos, and Collins defies the conclusions drawn by Albright and echoed by Mallon and Gleuck about this region’s initial settlement.
2. The conclusions drawn by these great pioneers of Levantine archaeology have gone unchallenged for almost a century.
3. Their conclusions have been accepted and taught in universities without question.
4. The result is that virtually every student of the history of this region is woefully ignorant of the rich and thriving culture that occupied this region during the Early, Intermediate, and Middle Bronze Ages.

Whatever their historical names may have been, their existence should no longer be ignored by Levantine studies and the maps representing the archaeological ages within the Levant. The data that is now available affirms the existence of these Bronze Age urban centers and suggests possible names for at least some of them. In this regard, I agree with Collins’ identifying them as: Sodom (Tall el-Hammam), Gomorrah (Tall Kafrayn), Admah (Tall Nimrin), and Zeboiim (plural in the Hebrew, which suggests the combination of Talls Bleibel and Mustah).

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